

Sensitivity of Clinical Features and Hemogram in Diagnosis of Megaloblastic Anemia in Patients with Pancytopenia with Etiopathogenesis**Moolrajani Kishore¹, Verma Suchita², Bansal Dharam Prakash³, Kumar Chitresh⁴, Rihwani Puneet⁵, Setia Mansi⁶, Kalra Vidita⁷, Parakh Rishabh⁸, Shah Sarthak⁹**^{1,3,5}Professor, Department, of General Medicine, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Hospital, Jaipur, Rajasthan^{2,4,6,7,8,9}Resident, Department of General Medicine, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Hospital, Jaipur, Rajasthan

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Abstract:**Background:** Pancytopenia, the simultaneous reduction of all three major blood elements-hemoglobin, leucocytes, and platelets- is a common hematological finding in clinical practice. This study focuses on the sensitivity of clinical features and hemogram in diagnosing Megaloblastic Anemia in pancytopenic patients, integrating epidemiological data and etiopathogenesis within the Indian context.**Materials and Methods:** This prospective hospital-based observational study was conducted at the Department of Medicine, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Hospital, over 18 months from October 2022 to March 2024. The study included patients admitted under the Department of General Medicine who met the criteria for pancytopenia. They were appropriately investigated and treated as per case.**Results:** Out of 202 patients, 25.2% were diagnosed with Megaloblastic Anemia, making it the most prevalent cause of pancytopenia. The study highlighted generalized weakness and pallor as the most common clinical features, with pallor showing significant diagnostic sensitivity (84.93%) and specificity (24%).**Conclusion:** The study underscores the critical role of clinical features in diagnosing Megaloblastic Anemia among pancytopenic patients in a resource-limited setting. As well as using a hemogram and reticulocyte count to differentiate megaloblastic anemia from other causes of pancytopenia. This emphasizes the need for critical awareness to improve early diagnosis and management of Megaloblastic Anemia, particularly in regions with high nutritional deficiencies.**Keywords:** Pancytopenia, Megaloblastic anemia, Iron Deficiency anemia, Reticulocyte Count, Mean corpuscular volume.

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Introduction

Peripheral pancytopenia is a reduction in all three major formed elements of blood to levels below their lower normal limit leading to simultaneous presence of anemia, leucopenia and thrombocytopenia. Thus, it is not a disease entity by itself, but rather a triad of findings [1]. It is a fairly common haematological finding encountered in routine clinical practice and physicians should have intimate knowledge of its various aetiologies and presentations.

Pancytopenia is a clinical manifestation of several underlying disorders ranging from non-malignant to malignant. Various aetiologies leading to a pancytopenic blood picture include- reduction in hematopoietic cell production as in aplastic anemia, nutritional deficiencies in Vitamin B12, folate and iron, infiltration of bone marrow by abnormal cells as in haematological malignancies, ineffective hematopoiesis with cell destruction as in

megaloblastic anemia, antibody-mediated destruction of cells as in autoimmune disorders, and splenic sequestration of cells as in hypersplenism. [2]

In the context of pancytopenia, megaloblastic anemia and aplastic anemia are the most common causes of pancytopenia in India [2,3]. In north-western India, where this study was conducted, megaloblastic anemia is the most common etiology of pancytopenia and this is likely due to the nutritional deficiencies that come with a vast vegetarian population. Megaloblastic anemia is characterized by a particular morphology of developing red cells in the marrow. Bone marrow is typically hypercellular with cause of anemia being ineffective erythropoiesis producing large red cells called macrocytes, and hypersegmented nuclei in neutrophils.

Clinical features of pancytopenia usually result from bone marrow failure such as pallor, generalised weakness, dyspnea, bleeding manifestations, prolonged fever, and increased tendency to infections [4]. Megaloblastic anemia also presents with similar complaints including vague symptoms such as easy fatigability and low grade fever. Gastrointestinal symptoms such as loss of appetite, glossitis, and diarrhoea may manifest. Paresthesia is a common neurological feature of Vitamin B12 deficiency. Peripheral neuropathy and sensory ataxia are unique to Vitamin B12 deficiency and can lead to permanent impairment if not treated promptly. [5]

It is imperative to be able to have high degree of suspicion for megaloblastic anemia as a cause of pancytopenia for the timely and cost-effective treatment of patients to prevent and reverse neurological manifestations in our population.

Materials and Methods

This was a prospective hospital-based observational study conducted at Department of Medicine, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Hospital, Jaipur. This study was approved by Institute Ethical Committee (MGMC&H/IEC/JPR/2022/1073).

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Age >18 years
2. Haemoglobin < 13 g/dL (male); < 12 g/dL (non-pregnant female)
3. Absolute Neutrophil Count <1500/mm³
4. Platelet Count < 150×10⁹/mm³
5. Written Informed Consent

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Patients who did not give consent
2. Pregnant females

Statistical Analysis: Statistical analyses were conducted using Microsoft Excel, focusing on frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation, and significant associations with a P value <0.05.

This study was carried out at the Department of Medicine, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Hospital, over an 18-month period from October 2022 to March 2024. Patients admitted under the Department of General Medicine who met the pancytopenia criteria were included in the study. These patients underwent a detailed medical history review and thorough physical examination. Various blood parameters were assessed, including Complete Blood Count (CBC), Reticulocyte Count, with bone marrow examinations conducted as clinically necessary. The study continued to follow these patients until their discharge. The sample size comprised all patients admitted to the Department of General Medicine who fulfilled the inclusion criteria, ensuring a comprehensive analysis of the factors at play in the diagnosis and management of pancytopenia. Treatment was given as appropriate to all patients.

Results

A total 202 patients were included in the study. Out of them 116 (57%) were males, and 86 (43%) were females (M:F :: 1.3:1). Mean age was 40 ±14 years. 160 patients (79%) follow a vegetarian diet, while 42 (21%) follow a non-vegetarian diet. 91 patients (45%) are smokers, 56 patients (28%) engage in tobacco chewing, and 33 patients (16%) consume alcohol. Figure 1 shows the distribution of lifestyle habits among study subjects.

Figure 1: Distribution of presence or absence of various lifestyle habits of patients

The most common presenting complaint was generalized weakness, present in 195 (97%) patients. Other complaints included fever (65%), weight loss (55%), abdominal pain (51%), paresthesia (47%) and dyspnea (47%). On detailed physical examination pallor was the most common feature, present in 160 patients (79%), followed by splenomegaly in

93 patients (46%) and pedal edema in 83 patients (41%). Least common findings were angular stomatitis (7%), gum hypertrophy (4%) and cyanosis (2%). Table 1 shows the distribution of presenting symptoms and clinical features of our patients and their sensitivity and specificity in diagnosing Megaloblastic anemia.

Table 1: Distribution of symptomatology and clinical features of patients with pancytopenia and their sensitivity and specificity in diagnosing megaloblastic anemia

Symptoms	Present	Sensitivity	Specificity
Generalized Weakness	195 (97%)	97%	4%
Fever	132 (65%)	56%	29%
Dyspnea	95 (47%)	48%	53%
Bone Pain	57 (28%)	16%	65%
Bleeding manifestations	48 (24%)	15%	71%
Weight loss	112 (55%)	51%	42%
Abdominal pain	103 (51%)	42%	44%
Mouth Ulcers	39 (19%)	29%	86%
Skin Rash	17 (8%)	10%	92%
Jaundice	66 (33%)	44%	74%
Paresthesia	94 (47%)	68%	66%
Clinical Features			
Pallor	160 (79%)	84.93%	24%
Icterus	67 (33%)	46.58%	74%
Cyanosis	4 (2%)	1.37%	98%
Clubbing	42 (21%)	13.70%	75%
Pedal Edema	83 (41%)	34.25%	55%
Lymphadenopathy	17 (8%)	6.85%	91%
Knuckle hyperpigmentation	52 (26%)	50.68%	88%
Angular stomatitis	14 (7%)	12.33%	96%
Glossitis	20 (10%)	15.07%	93%
Bleeding manifestations	44 (22%)	13.70%	74%
Sternal tenderness	35 (17%)	17.81%	83%
Gum hypertrophy	8 (4%)	5.48%	97%
Splenomegaly	93 (46%)	45.21%	53%

After diagnosing the patient, this study discovered that 51 patients (25.2%) had Megaloblastic Anemia as the underlying pathology. 25 patients (12.4%) had Iron Deficiency Anemia, which may have been a mislabeled microcytic anemia due to other causes as bone marrow study was not performed on all patients. 15 patients had tropical fever which included malaria, dengue fever and scrub typhus which are endemic to this region. 14 (6.9%) had

chronic liver disease which is a growing cause of pancytopenia presenting to tertiary care centers. Aplastic Anemia and Hepatitis each affected 10 patients (5.0%). Leukaemia was seen in 7 patients (3.5%), and chronic kidney disease in 6 patients (3.0%). 17 (8.4%) patients had unspecified pancytopenia. Table 2 provides a comprehensive list of the final diagnoses of patients.

Table 2: Distribution of diagnosis of pancytopenia cases

CKD- Chronic Kidney Disease, CLD- Chronic Liver disease, ITP- Immune Thrombocytopenic Purpura, RVD- Retroviral disease, SLE- Systemic Lupus Erythematosus

Diagnoses	No. of patients	Percentage
Megaloblastic anemia	51	25.20%
Iron Deficiency Anemia	25	12.40%
Undefined Pancytopenia	17	8.40%
Tropical Fever	15	7.40%

Aplastic anemia	10	5.00%
Hepatitis	10	5.00%
Leukaemia	7	3.50%
CKD	6	3.00%
CLD	4	2.00%
Malignancy	4	2.00%
Myelodysplastic syndrome	4	2.00%
Haemolytic anemia	4	2.00%
Dimorphic Anemia	4	2.00%
ITP	4	2.00%
Hypothyroidism	4	2.00%
Tuberculosis	2	1.00%
Sarcoidosis	2	1.00%
Autoimmune hepatitis	2	1.00%
Multiple myeloma	2	1.00%
Drug induced pancytopenia	3	1.50%
RVD	3	1.50%
SLE	3	1.50%
Sheehan's syndrome	1	0.50%
Non-Hodgkin's Lymphoma	1	0.50%
Enteric fever	1	0.50%
Chronic Lymphoproliferative Disorder	1	0.50%
Lymphoma	1	0.50%
Thalassemia Major	1	0.50%

Figure 2 shows the distribution of hemoglobin levels, total leucocyte count (TLC), platelet count, reticulocyte count and mean corpuscular volume (MCV) of patients of megaloblastic anaemia (n=73). Most patients had a hemoglobin ≤ 5 g/dL, TLC >2500 cells/mm³, platelet count $<50,000$ cells/mm³, normal reticulocyte count and MCV >101 fL.

Figure 2: Distribution of ranges of CBC parameters in patients of Megaloblastic anaemia with pancytopenia

In this study, the sensitivity of high MCV in diagnosing megaloblastic anemia in pancytopenia is 69.86%, and the specificity is 87%. The p-value is less than 0.001 indicating a highly significant statistical association between high MCV values and megaloblastic anemia. The sensitivity of having a reticulocyte count less than 0.5% in diagnosing

megaloblastic anemia is 35.62%, and the specificity is 80%. The statistical analysis shows a p-value of 0.0157, indicating a significant correlation, suggesting a modest degree of statistical significance in the association between reticulocyte count and the presence of megaloblastic anaemia (Table 3).

Table 3: Sensitivity, specificity and significance of patients with pancytopenia according to mean corpuscular volume (MCV) value and reticulocyte count (n=202) with chi-square test

MCV (fL)	Megaloblastic anemia present	Megaloblastic anemia absent	Sensitivity	Specificity	p-value	χ^2 (1, n=202)
MCV >101	51	17	69.86%	87%	< .001	67.08
MCV ≤101	22	112				
Reticulocyte Count (%)						
<0.5	26	26	35.62%	80%	0.0157	5.83
≥0.5	47	103				

Discussion

The study was conducted in the state of Rajasthan, India which has limited clinical studies showing the etiological and clinical profile of patients with pancytopenia. The present study aims at bridging that gap and providing more data for future studies in the field. Along with that, the study aims to find the sensitivity of various clinical features to diagnose megaloblastic anemia which is a common nutritional anemia in these regions due to a vast vegetarian population. Also because of the widespread access to health services in the state of Rajasthan many patients which suspected megaloblastic anemia already arrive at our tertiary care hospital treated with at least one dose of injectable Vitamin B12 supplementation. This makes the standard test of serum Vitamin B12 for diagnosing nutritional megaloblastic anemia of little use. Thus, clinicians must use other diagnostic tools available to make the diagnosis. In this study the aim is to determine the sensitivity of clinical features, significance of CBC and reticulocyte count in diagnosis of Megaloblastic anemia in patients with pancytopenia.

Vishnoi et al [6] in Udaipur, Rajasthan had a male to female ratio, with 57.58% male and 42.42% female patients in their study of 132 patients of pancytopenia. This is comparable to our own study which had 57% males and 43% female cases. The mean age in our study was 40 ± 14 years and most 20% of the patients were in the age group of 60 years or more which is in contrast with a study conducted by Grover et al [7] in Delhi, India in 2018 which had a majority of their 90 cases presenting to their emergency department in the age group of 18-29 years. The reason for such a difference may be that patients admitted to the Department of General Medicine such as in our case are of a more varied background and those

presenting to an emergency setting may be a different subset of the population.

Lifestyle habits such as diet, tobacco smoking, chewing, and alcohol consumption were also noted in our study. In this region tobacco smoking is common among both males and females and our study showed that 45% of the patients were smokers, 28% of chewed tobacco, and 16% consumed alcohol. There have not been any studies comparing the relation of tobacco smoking to pancytopenia in this region, but Vivek et al [8] in Uttarakhand conducted a case control study in which there was strong relation between smoking- particularly beedi smoking, which is what is common among patients of the present study as well- and iron deficiency anemia, which was the second most common diagnosed cause of pancytopenia in our study. In the study, most (79%) of the patients were vegetarian, which is possibly a reason why our study demonstrated about a quarter of the pancytopenia patients had underlying megaloblastic anaemia.

The present study had megaloblastic anemia as the most common (25.2%) cause of pancytopenia in our population studied. This is comparable to other studies conducted in the Indian subcontinent such as Chandra et al [9] who had 25% of pancytopenia had underlying pancytopenia. Vishnoi et al [6], and Varma et al [10] had results at 57% and 39% respectively. Aplastic anemia was the second most common cause of pancytopenia in most studies where it wasn't the first cause which is in stark contrast with our study where the second most common cause was Iron Deficiency anemia (IDA). While IDA can cause pancytopenia when prolonged deficiency moves to a preference for erythropoiesis in leu of megakaryocyte pancytopenia may develop [11], we suggest the reason for this being a mislabelling due to lack of definitive bone marrow examinations done to

confirm aplastic anemia as a diagnosis. [12] Tropical fever was another cause of pancytopenia which is common (17%) in this part of the world with many patients of Malaria, Dengue Fever and Scrub typhus presenting with pancytopenia and bleeding manifestations that quickly reverses with appropriate treatment and blood product transfusions as necessary.

The most common presenting complaint was generalized weakness (97%) followed by fever (65%) and weight loss (55%). Other subcontinental studies [1-4, 6] had a similar profile of most common features, but in comparison our study subjects less frequently presented with the complaint of shortness of breath. The reason for this is the anemia component of pancytopenia which usually presents with vague feelings of malaise in a patient which then manifests as low-grade fever, shortness of breath on exertion and weight loss is there is a chronic underlying etiology for the pancytopenia. The least common presenting complaints were skin rashes (8%) and mouth ulcers (19%).

The most common clinical feature was pallor (79%) and this was found as the most common in studies across the board. Splenomegaly (46%) was the second most common clinical feature in our study and was similarly in studies conducted by Jain et al. [12] Cyanosis and gum hypertrophy were the least common presentations at 2% and 4% incidence respectively.

It was noted there was not much difference between the total leucocyte count and platelet counts of all patients with megaloblastic anaemia and patients with other causes of pancytopenia, but there was a significant difference in hemoglobin levels. While the cause is unknown it may be due to higher levels of bone marrow suppression seen in Vitamin B12 deficiencies due to DNA damage. Both an MCV >101fL and Reticulocyte count <0.5% have a significant relation with megaloblastic anaemia in patients with pancytopenia which was also corroborated by a study in the same population as Yadav et al. [13]

Conclusion

The most common underlying pathology of pancytopenia in our study was Megaloblastic anemia due to Vitamin B12 deficiency, followed by Iron Deficiency Anemia. Most of the patients of pancytopenia were over 60 years of age and among them most patients with megaloblastic anemia were below the age of 30 years. The presenting complaint of generalized weakness has high sensitivity anemia but very low specificity but complaints such as skin rash, mouth ulcers and jaundice had higher specificity to diagnose megaloblastic anemia. Clinical features of pallor similarly had high sensitivity but low specificity. Gum hypertrophy, angular stomatitis, and glossitis have the highest specificity

of diagnosing megaloblastic anemia. MCV >101fL and reticulocyte count <0.5% are useful and statistically significant diagnostic markers to determine megaloblastic anemia in a patient with pancytopenia.

With this study we have created a profile of patients with pancytopenia, their lifestyle habitus as well as the common presenting complaints, clinical features and hemogram findings. This will contribute to a growing group of studies that will help physicians diagnose megaloblastic anemia with greater accuracy and less financial burden to the patient.

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